

CREATING A VARIETY SAMPLE OF PATISSON PLANT (CUCURBITA PEPO VAR. MELOPEPO) AND STUDYING USEFUL PROPERTIES

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Annotatsiya. Mamlakatimizning ko'plab hududlari uchun an'anaviy bo'lgan patisson o'simligi ekib o'rganilmoqda. Bu sabzavot o'simligi o'zining foydali xususiyatlari bilan mashhur. Uning foydali xususiyatlari dietologlar tomonidan ham tan olingan. Shu sababli buyrak va jigar kasalliklari, shuningdek, oshqozon yarasi va ateroskleroz uchun patissonni ko'proq tavsiya qilishadi. Patisson mevalarida vitaminlar, oson hazm bo'ladigan uglevodlar, pektin moddalari va mineral tuzlar majmuasi mavjudligi sababli mutlaqo sog'lom odamlar uchun foydalidir, bu proteinli ovqatlarning yaxshiroq so'rilishiga va qonning ishqoriy reaksiyasini saqlab turishga yordam beradi.

Abstract. The patisson plant, which is traditional for many regions of our country, is being cultivated. This vegetable plant is famous for its useful properties. Its useful properties are also recognized by nutritionists. For this reason, patisson is more recommended for kidney and liver diseases, as well as stomach ulcers and atherosclerosis. Patisson fruits are useful for absolutely healthy people due to the presence of a complex of vitamins, easily digestible carbohydrates, pectin substances and mineral salts, which help to better absorb protein foods and maintain the alkaline reaction of the blood.

Kalit so'zlar. Patisson navining dastlabki namunalarini agrobiologik baholash, manba materialini o'rganish, duragaylarini yaratish, foydali xususiyatlarini o'rganish.

Key words. Agrobiological evaluation of the first samples of Patisson variety, study of source material, creation of hybrids, study of useful properties.

Enter. Research conditions and methods. The research was conducted in 2020 in the fields of Surkhondarya region, Termiz district, Termiz institute of agro-technologies and innovative development, using the methods of laboratory and field experiments, along with additional analysis. The study was conducted by independent researcher Kenjayeva T.R. was carried out by, in which 18 varieties of patisson were planted. Sow seeds in open ground in 2-3 ten days of April, each

It was carried out according to the scheme of 0.9 x 1.0 m in single-row plots consisting of 10 plants from the sample. The area of the experimental plot was 9 m². Hybrids were evaluated according to the set of economically valuable characters. The Aq-13 variety was used as a control

Figure 1. Research site

The purpose and objectives of the research. The purpose of the work is to study and select the source material for the creation of new varieties of patisson.

Scientific innovation of research results. As a result of the study of Patisson's collection varieties, the sources of the main economic valuable characters were determined.

Figure 2. Patisson fruit.

During the growing season of Patisson, phenological observations were made, planting dates, germination and mass germination, flowering of male flowers, flowering of female flowers, fruiting and ripening of fruits were recorded Economically valuable characters of Patisson -

productivity, early maturity, taste evaluation and accounting is done.

Patissonning morfologik xususiyatlari baholandi: o'simlikning turi va shakli, poyasining shoxlanishi, barglari, poyalari va poyalarining o'sishi, barg va meva belgilari.

Research results. Characteristics of varieties of patisson, morphological characteristics of 18 patisson samples, source material were studied in detail. When evaluating the compact growth of the bush, Malakhite, Cheburashka, and Solnishko varieties stood out. Stem branching is weak to moderate in most specimens. An important morphological feature in the collection and care of plants is the growth of

.Consumption

Smooth and because the thornless stems and leaves are smaller

has a known value. According to the shape of the fruit, examples of the pumpkin-shaped, round-flat, kungura-shaped variety were recorded.

The studied varieties include white (Disk, Cheburashka), green (Gosha, Bingo-Bongo, Chunga-Changa), cream (Pyatachok, Zontik), yellow (Fuete, Orange) fruit color samples.

The Solnishko variety is superior to other varieties, the fruits of this sample are distinguished by their quick ripening and abundance, and their consumption is very soft.

CONCLUSIONS.

Vegetables are the most valuable food product of particular importance.

The importance and indispensability of vegetables in nutrition is that they are suppliers of carbohydrates, vitamins, essential oils, mineral salts, and phytoncides necessary for the normal functioning of the living organism

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